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Benchmarking Deep Neural Networks on space compatible hardware for EO data extraction and reduction

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ABSTRACT

The current trend for institutional satellite missions is to push for an increase of the spatial and spectral resolution of image products, possibly with a higher revisit time, thus increasing the volume of acquired data. Moreover, the development of small satellites missions introduces new configurations where resources are more limited. Therefore, the downlink capacities become a bottleneck when the objective is to forward all the data to ground stations for their analysis. One of the most radical solutions to lighten this burden is to directly bring on board some of the tools used to extract information. This will leave the possibility of discarding useless or noisy images or even to analyse completely the images on board and downlink only the images with specific objects of interest for example.

However, bringing efficient analysis algorithms on board is not a straightforward operation. We focus here on deep learning algorithms known to be very efficient for many images analysis tasks. Many constraints due to the context of on-board processing must be considered. First, the neural networks must be simplified and compressed in order to fit on the available hardware. It means simplifying the architecture of the networks and also quantifying all variables and computations with short floating-point numbers or even integers with a very low number of bits. Then, the networks must be translated and deployed on the hardware available whether it is a small CPU, a SoC FPGA or even an ASIC. Finally, the processing carried out by the algorithm must achieve acceptable performances in terms of throughput and power consumption. It is also essential to verify that there is no significant loss of accuracy compared to the same processing carried out on ground.

The work presented aims at evaluating the performance in terms of throughput, power consumption and accuracy that can be achieved by such applications. Several use cases are considered starting from cloud segmentation, then cloud versus snow discrimination, to more specific applications, namely forest segmentation and vessel detection. All these applications have been implemented to compare the performances between the large networks used on ground and the small networks usable on board. All these simplified algorithms were then tested on a set of devices including Xilinx Zynq UltraScale+, Xilinx Zynq 7000 Series, AMD G-Series, Xilinx Kintex Ultrascale KU040 and Intel Myriad 2. This set of device gives a representative view on the performances that can be achieved with different family of device (SoC FPGA, CPU, ASICs). It is important to note that these performances are directly linked to the software tools delivered by the constructors of the devices or the available specific backends. Limited results can thus be linked to inherent limitation of the device or to a lack of maturity of the software used to run neural networks on the device.

This study allows us to present important figures regarding achievable power consumptions, throughput, and performances of deep neural networks at the edge for essential EO use cases.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade, the technological improvements in compute capabilities and miniaturization of processing payloads have enabled the development of affordable platforms, with the production of small satellites below 10kg featuring a

reasonable computing power. This reduction has brought new actors in the space markets targeting a wide range of applications, in particular in Earth Observation. However, one of the most limiting factors for this application is reduce bandwidth due to reduced power budget [15] to download acquired data on ground. The use of intelligent payload is extensively studied since taking decision directly on-board or discard uninteresting images could drastically reduce this burden. Even though it is very promising, there are other major constraints due to the spatial environment such as power availability, compute and memory requirements, and compatible payload for executing such computation intensive algorithm as deep neural networks (DNN) on board.

Many research papers address the problem of training simplified neural network using distillation [1], pruning [2], binary neural networks [3]. Our previous work detailed in [4,5] presents the simplification methods we use. Fewer articles also evaluate on-board performance, and provide an overview of the main opportunities and problems [6,7]. A clear opportunity is brought by FPGA [8,9] and Myriad VPU [10], even if traditional embedded CPU are also targeted but required a lot of software optimisation [11] to be competitive. Our study tries to benchmark a wide variety of devices with various use cases.

The remaining of this article is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly introduces the use cases selected to perform the benchmark and the reduction method used to obtain the simplified neural networks. Section 3 details the set of hardware platforms that have been tested with their pros and cons. The results in terms of application performance and throughput are then presented in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the output of this study.

2 USE CASES

Four use cases have been studied in order to assess the performances of deep neural network (DNN) in various contexts. The following use cases were selected:

- a semantic segmentation of clouds to produce cloud masks identifying clouds at a pixel level,
- its enhanced version to distinguish snow from clouds. Clouds and snow may be difficult to distinguish and train an algorithm to distinguish them specifically improves the performances of the cloud detection task,
- a semantic segmentation of forest to detect the change in forest areas, especially in deforested regions,
- a bounding boxes boat detection for vessel traffic monitoring/surveillance and illegal activities detection.

All the details concerning the database used or the type of the model are presented in the Table 1. At least one model was trained for each use cases. However, there is synergy between the use cases in particular with the cloud coverage use case which can reduce the amount of data to be processed. The cloud coverage use case is a two-class problem (clouds and not-clouds). For the deforestation use case, at first, two-class models (forest and other) were trained, then a third class for the clouds was added to increase the model performances. The vessel detection is a one-class detection problem (boat). Finally, the snow-vs.-clouds problem is a three-class problem (snow – clouds – other).

The model architectures are not detailed in this article since they were detailed in previous works [4,5]. However, the models can be described as light version of the well-known Unet [12] and SSD [13] networks.

2.1 IMPACT ON DATA COMPRESSION

The selected use cases are not intended to improve the image quality but aims at filtering the images and reducing the amount of data to be processed on board and downlinked on ground. Embedding the algorithm on the satellite prevents the users from downloading all acquired images on ground and allow take decision on-board and to select for download only the images of interest.

The first use case has been built to detect clouds in an image and to discard cloudy images or cloudy parts of the images before compression for downlink or other processing. It is mandatory to detect clouds when the acquisition aims to observe objects close to the ground. For instance, the mission Sentinel-2 (S2) of the Copernicus program shows that over France there is a yearly average of 56% of cloudy pixels in the acquired image (see Fig. 1). Since the clouds are often large continuous objects, they can be removed from image acquired for compression. This results, in theory, in a 56% reduction of the number of pixels to be processed.

The second use case aims to detect the changes in forest areas by extracting forests information (mask, surface, etc.) and compared it to a reference base. It can then provide statistics on the state of the forest, send alarms if there is an anomaly and flags the images containing forest to downlink them.

Table 1. Use cases and models description

Use case	DNN method	Input data	Model type
Cloud coverage	Segmentation	Aerosol+RGB+NIR (Sentinel-2 10m)	Unet like
Deforestation	Change detection	RGB+NIR (Sentinel-2 10m)	Unet like
Vessel Detection	Bounding boxes detection	RGB, HR Airbus Ship Detection Challenge	SSD like
Snow vs. Clouds	Segmentation	RGB+NIR (Sentinel-2 10m)	Unet like

Fig. 1. Cloud Cover over France using all Sentinel 2 products between 01-2016 and 12-2021 made by Agenium Space (40552 acquisitions)

The third use case purpose is to detect boats. It can be used to follow vessel movements and identify illegal activities. Moreover, it prevents from downloading a lot of sea images without any boat by choosing a window around the detected boat and thus downloading considerably fewer images.

The last use case is an improvement of the first one in which the snow was added to differentiate snow from clouds. This improvement is needed when the satellite makes acquisitions in snow areas or when the acquisitions are done in winter. This improvement can also be used, like for the forest use case, to measure the surface of snow and compare with previous data. It is also interesting to note that this task is generally done using the SWIR bands and this study shows that it is also feasible with only RGB-NIR bands that are more common in small satellites.

2.2 MODELS REDUCTION

To be adapted to an embedded environment, the trained models have been simplified. The simplification focuses on reducing three criteria:

- the number of parameters in the model to make the model uploadable through limited bandwidth of a satellite,
- the memory footprint to make the model runnable on a limited memory embedded system,
- the workload per input of the model to make the model runnable on a device with limited power consumption and computing capabilities within a reasonable execution time.

There are various simplification methods, among which the most known are pruning, distillation, quantization, and codebooks. The models have been simplified using distillation and quantization. The distillation process used is the same for every use case and targeted devices [4]. It results in a compression of 2 of the number of operation per input and from 17 to 120 of the number of parameter. The quantization used differs from a device to another. The models executed on FPGA were quantified to 8bits integer, while the models executed on CPU and ASIC were quantified to 16 bits floating points resulting respectively to a compression factor of 4 and 2 of the parameters' stored size.

3 HARDWARE

We developed a generic pipeline applicable to different deep neural networks architectures to facilitate the DNN simplification and deployment on an embedded device. The Fig. 2 describes the global process.

Various payloads are targeted including SoC (System on Chip) FPGA, embedded CPU and ASIC. All devices are either space qualified or already used in space. This section describes first, the different hardware used and their respective workflow in section 3.1 and 3.2, then constraints and limit of DNN on those payloads.

Fig. 2. General device agnostic process for on-board deployment

3.1 FPGA / SOC FPGA

FPGA or SoC FPGA are commonly used in satellites. They are very flexible and have a lot of built-in parallelism for a low power consumption making them a good solution to implement DNN at the edge while keeping a low-latency and a high throughput. This study targeted three FPGA devices detailed in the Table 2.

The deployment on hardware is generally a complex and tedious task. In particular, the development of a VHDL code that could be synthesized and ported on a device is very difficult since hardware design depends on the device characteristics (memory size, bloc composition, interconnection structure, ...). To summarize, it is not possible to go through this step if you want to fast prototyping and design a deployment pipeline in a reasonable cost. For this reason, it appears to be more practical and safer to rely on the software suite provided by the hardware manufacturer.

Xilinx provide a tool named Vitis AI allowing to follow the workflow described in Fig. 3., for DPU instructions generation. In this example, we assume that a Keras model was generated as output of the simplification step. The first step is to convert the model in a model compatible with VITIS AI tools typically a TensorFlow, Caffe or Pytorch model with a specific version. Additionally, the user should verify that all layers and their parameters are supported by VITIS AI and the target device. Otherwise, it means that the architecture selected for distillation was not appropriate and that it should be redone in a compatible architecture.

The second step consists in quantizing the model. It is necessary first because the VITIS AI accelerator only supports integer operations and, because reducing the number of bits used for weights and for activations is a way to optimize the throughput of the system. The quantization of weights can be done directly with the model, but it is important to underline that the quantization of activations necessitates a set of calibration images in order to estimate the distribution of activations for each layer. VITIS AI provides a quantization tool that uses a symmetric linear quantization. This tool generates a quantized model and also an evaluation model. This evaluation model can be run on a conventional computer using the modified TensorFlow library provided in VITIS AI. It allows to simulate the behaviour of the model on the DPU and eventually to validate the quantized model or adjust the number of bits used to quantify.

Finally, the last step is the compilation of the quantized model. The compiler provided by the manufacturer converts the quantized model, still in a protobuf format, into ELF object files and produces kernel information for deployment. During the compilation, several optimizations are also performed such as the fusion of batch norm layers with the preceding convolution layer. It can be noted that the last step is quite different on the latest version of VITIS AI.

There is a difference of implementation between FPGA and SoC FPGA because a CPU is needed to drive the FPGA accelerator. Since the Kintex Ultrascale (see Table 2.) is an FPGA, it doesn't have any CPU part and it is not natively supported by VITIS AI tools. It was necessary to add a Microblaze CPU on the logic of the FPGA to drive the accelerator and adapt the work done on SoC FPGA.

Fig. 3. Workflow for Xilinx IP acceleration

Table 2. Devices and environment description

Device	Space qualification	Type	Board	Quantization	Framework
Zynq Ultrascale+	Qualified	SoC FPGA	ZCU102 (ZU9EG)	Symmetric Int8	Vitis AI 1.2
Zynq 7000 series	Soon used in space	SoC FPGA	ZedBoard (Z7020)	Symmetric Int8	Vitis AI 1.2
Kintex Ultrascale	Qualified	FPGA	KCU105 (KU040)	Symmetric Int8	Vitis AI 1.3
AMD G-series	Used in space	SoC CPU/GPU	iX5 (Unibap)	FP16	TensorFlow Lite 2.4.3
Intel Movidius Myriad 2	Used in space	ASIC	Intel Movidius Neural Compute Stick	FP16	Intel OpenVINO 2020.3

3.2 CPU / ASIC

In addition to FPGAs, two other devices have been tested (see Table 2.). The first is an AMD G-series which is an embedded SoC composed of an AMD CPU and an integrated GPU. The second is an Intel Movidius Myriad 2 VPU which is an ASIC dedicated for DNN inference. These devices are less flexible than the FPGA, however they have already been embedded in a satellite [10,14], thus they are a good basis for comparison. Compared to FPGA, the deployment of neural network on those devices is faster and simpler than on FPGA, since they don't require hardware design.

Indeed, the AMD device natively supports DNN libraries such as Tensorflow or Pytorch since it is a CPU/GPU SoC. The Tensorflow Lite framework was used for this device. In order to speed up the inference and reduce the size of the models, a quantization was applied before running the model. Since the AMD device doesn't support AVX2 instructions set, there is no SIMD instructions for 8bits integer. As a consequence, only a 16 bits floating point quantization was applied. However, the use of GPU is more complex with Tensorflow Lite than with Tensorflow since the GPU bindings are only available through the C++ API.

Intel provides a tool named OpenVINO used to do and optimize neural networks inference on Intel devices (CPU, GPU, ASIC, ...). The first step is to convert the model to the intermediate representation used by Intel with OpenVINO. This step also includes the quantization and some other parametrized optimization transformations applied to the model. Since the Myriad VPU only supports 16 bits floating-point inference, the model was quantized to be supported by the Myriad VPU. Then, the intermediate representation model is used to run the inference on the VPU with OpenVINO drivers.

3.3 MODELS EMBEDABILITY / CONSTRAINTS

Executing any algorithm on an embedded context is much more constrained than on a workstation environment. The power is often more limited, and the device capabilities, in terms of memory and computation capacity, is much lower than on a machine learning workstation. Thus, executing such memory and computation intensive algorithm as DNN models on embedded devices is complex. To fit in the power constraints, it is mandatory to reduce the power consumption. To reduce the power consumption, it is possible to act on two parameters. First, the number of operations the algorithm uses per input to produce an output (workload per input) and second, the memory footprint of the model, it means how many bytes the model uses to store its parameters and do the computations. The simplification step is important to allow the models to run on an embedded context. However, despite this reduction, the manufacturer tools have some limitations concerning the layer supported and the parameter ranges of supported layers. Thus, it is mandatory to take into account during the simplification process the layer supported by the targeted device. The AMD G-series and the Myriad VPU are less restrictive on the layer supported than the FPGA. Since the first is a general-purpose device (CPU) and supports a lot of operation and the second is designed to support the inference of common state-of-the-art models, or at least their light versions. While the IP used in VITIS AI is not intended to support all state-of-the-art models but modified version for embedded environments of those models. As a consequence, the model simplified have been created to fit the limitations of the VITIS AI IP.

4 BENCHMARKS RESULTS

This section contains the results of the tests. We performed exhaustive tests, each model use case has been tested on each device. First, we evaluate the drop of prediction capabilities (f1-score) between the pre-quantification simplified model executed in a machine learning environment and the simplified and quantized model executed in an embedded environment. Then, the efficiency of the on-board implementation is measured on all tested devices.

4.1 LOSS (PREDICTION CAPABILITIES) / PERFORMANCE DROP

When reducing algorithms in order to execute them in an embedded environment, the loss of performances between the original algorithm and the final version executed at the edge is a metric of major importance. This part does not include the loss of performance during the model simplification but only between the simplified model and the execution on board. The Table 3 shows the best f1-score results per use case and per devices among all the models trained.

All FPGA and SoC FPGA targeted are Xilinx devices. They are referred to as Xilinx devices in this section. Moreover, since the same acceleration IP has been used on several boards and under various configuration a preliminary comparison has been done between the results of the different board and configuration. These tests showed that the results are bit perfect regardless of the board and configuration with the IP accelerator.

The quantization has little impact on the performance. Indeed, the quantization on 16 bits floating-point for the AMD and the Myriad devices have near zero performance drop, while the quantization on 8 bits integer for Xilinx devices presents a higher drop of performance. However, this does not exceed 0.05 on the f1-score.

Moreover, the drop of performance is higher for the semantic segmentation than for the bounding box detection (Vessel Detection). It is explained by the fact that the detection post-processing is more aggressive than the semantic segmentation post-processing and act like a filtering of the results. Indeed, the post-processing of the detection filters the boxes with the highest score and discard all the boxes that detect the same object by discarding the boxes which overlaps over some threshold [13]. On the contrary, the segmentation post-processing is only a SoftMax between the different classes predicted. Also, the semantic segmentation is a difficult task since it consists of classify each pixel of an image.

4.2 THROUGHPUT & POWER

To characterize the efficiency of on-board implementation, two parameters have been measured: the throughput of the implementation in terms of pixels per seconds (pixels/s) and the power consumption in Watts (W). The two elements are mixed in a throughput per Watts (pixels/s/W). The pixels are multi-channels pixels with a number of channels depending on the use case. The Table 4 presents the throughputs per Watt for the best selected models for each use case, the models are consistent with the models presented in the Table 3.

The Myriad VPU and the Zynq Ultrascale+ (ZU+) are the most efficient devices, with a better result for Myriad on very small model (Deforestation) and better results for the ZU+ on detection task. However, the Myriad VPU tests does not include the execution of the post-processing of the model nor the loading of the input image and saving of the results. Those tasks are done on a CPU driving the Myriad VPU and are not taken into account while measuring throughput and power consumption. Indeed, the Myriad VPU is only a deep neural network accelerator, and it is not possible to run such tasks on it. While the tests for the ZU+ device include the full execution of the models with the consumption of the whole system.

The Zynq 7020 FPGA has less resources than the ZU+ FPGA used. The configuration of the acceleration IP used to infer the deep neural network on the ZU+ was too big to fit in the resources of the chip. As a consequence, the configuration has been modified to reduce the resources used and the capacity of the accelerator resulting in less efficient implementation.

The implementation on Kintex Ultrascale is more complex since there is no CPU on this device. A Microblaze CPU IP was used to drive the neural network accelerator. However, the Microblaze CPU has much less capacities than the CPU of the Zynq family devices. Thus, the performance of the system is more limited than the other Xilinx implementation. Moreover, the Kintex Ultrascale is not among the devices supported by VITIS AI tools which makes the implementation less efficient than the one with Zynq family devices. The results of this implementation are very slow due to the lack of capabilities of the CPU and a very slow communication between the Microblaze CPU and the acceleration IP. Nevertheless, it is possible to improve the efficiency of the device by implementing a part of the calculation on the FPGA, to reduce the load of the CPU.

Concerning the AMD G-series, several inference methods were tested, with Tensorflow and Tensorflow Lite, with the integrated GPU and without. The results presented are the best we could obtained, despite some incompatibilities between our models and Tensorflow Lite, especially when using the GPU. The device is 10 to 28 times less efficient than the Myriad VPU or the ZU+ but presents the advantage of running on CPU (or integrated GPU) which is available on any spatialized payloads.

Table 3. Best f1-score results per use case per device

	Model Parameters	Simplified model	AMD G-Series	Intel Movidius Myriad 2	Xilinx devices
Cloud Coverage	1 million	Other – 0.96 Cloud – 0.84	Other – 0.96 Cloud – 0.84	Other – 0.96 Cloud – 0.84	Other – 0.96 Cloud – 0.79
Deforestation	0.1 million	Other – 0.87 Forest – 0.92	Other – 0.87 Forest – 0.92	Other – 0.86 Forest – 0.92	Other – 0.82 Forest – 0.90
Vessel Detection	1 million	Boat - 0.82	Boat - 0.82	Boat - 0.82	Boat - 0.81
Snow VS Cloud	0.5 million	Other – 0.86 Cloud – 0.75 Snow – 0.85	Other – 0.86 Cloud – 0.75 Snow – 0.85	Other – 0.86 Cloud – 0.75 Snow – 0.85	Other – 0.84 Cloud – 0.72 Snow – 0.85

Table 4. Best throughput (px/s/W) per use case per device

	Model Parameters	AMD G-Series	Intel Movidius Myriad 2	Zynq Ultrascale+ (ZU9EG)	Zynq 7020	Xilinx Kintex Ultrascale (KU040)
Cloud Coverage	1 million	7,900	172,030	175,900	67,550	575
Deforestation	0.1 million	18,540	317,200	212,380	119,380	640
Vessel Detection	1 million	13,990	537,300	572,730	167,540	3060
Snow VS Cloud	0.5 million	8,570	209,000	185,490	76,880	435

5 CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORKS

To sum-up we have shown through the use cases addressed in this paper that we can reliably train DNN on ground, simplify them (from x17 to x120) to ease their port on COTS/space compliant HW and port them using the manufacturer's tools in order to filter and reduce the amount of data processed and downlinked to the ground. In the end, we have reliable DNN running on-board with accuracy performances on par with on ground performances and a good efficiency for the most promising devices.

Some may advocate that the dependency to third party IP for running DNN can be circumvented by redeveloping the required blocks for inference. This is true but, it will be pretty costly unless inhouse specific IP already exists. Note also that, in the coming years we are to expect a larger offer for such DPU related IP, eventually each manufacturer will have its own AI suite, enabling more choices on the actual HW chips.

The latest version of VITIS AI tools seems to provide better inference efficiency. Preliminary tests showed that a two times better efficiency is reachable. Moreover, for the FPGAs devices, implementing a hardware pre- and post-processing can also improve the implementation efficiency. In addition, targeting more aggressive quantization can be beneficial to the efficiency. Therefore, we are developing an IP to run binary neural networks on FPGAs.

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